

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D9.4

Online materials

November 2021

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The main objective of MES-CoBraD (Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders) is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in the Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependences through Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols, in light of the MES-CoBraD Agreement and associated challenges.

Towards this notion, MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.

The MES-CoBraD project aims at addressing all the challenges (clinical, research and technological) and also enhances efforts that harmonise and integrate the outcome, by maximising individual researchers' impact through collaborative value creation and Open Science practices. The platform of the MES-CoBraD project will provide a module (MES-CoBraD Expert System) which aims at improving personalized medicine approaches in real-world practice.

This report, the Online Material, mainly outlines the ways that the MES-CoBraD can share the scope and results with the appropriate audiences. More specifically, all the ways that the project is visually available are outlined in this report.

First of all, the website and the social media of the project are presented, because these means are the most important to the dissemination and communication strategy of the project as well as all the other materials and tools such as blogs, events, newsletters, infographics and videos.

Last but not least, the promotional means to be used are outlined. These include but are not limited to the MES-CoBraD logo and other standard dissemination means, such as those described in the visual identity of the project - D9.3 "Promotional and Informational material"; while more specialised means, including flyer, poster, leaflet and articles will be a core aspect of the project's online material.

1 THE MES-COBRA D WEBSITE

Project's Website is a dedicated dissemination and communication tool that is created in order to promote the project and to provide informative material that will be readily available on-line to all the potential audiences.

The MES-CoBraD Website¹ operates as the major source of information about the project's identity and goals. The Website is dedicated with the project information, objectives, results, partners, events and news from which every stakeholder category can be informed. In other words, MES-CoBraD website is a central tool of the project that provides secure access to the participants, hosts a project agenda and an e-library with the project's confidential management documents. Furthermore, the website includes a portal for sustained longitudinal studies and participant engagement. The website also promotes transparency of the project's scientific capabilities, processes, and results, by providing background information and a direct link to the MES-CoBraD platform. Furthermore, the website provides information about the project, its main objectives and description of the project's platform and knowledge, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which MES-CoBraD will participate in, also information about project partners and related projects. What is more, the website presents information to stakeholder groups so that they will understand the reasons to get involved and how they can participate in the project's activities. Last but not least the website provides a common reference for interested stakeholders to all the produces content, including the MES-CoBraD Solution, details of activities, etc.

The website is already online and functional and consists of several information webpages, mainly on the action (about, pilots, solution, platform, synergies) as well as pages showcasing specific activities (e.g., news & events, communication, materials) or major outcomes, namely reports, publications, infographics, etc. Moreover, the website will be updated periodically (at least once a month) throughout the project and present the progress of it. It is worth mentioned that the public deliverables that are developed throughout the project's lifetime are available to download from the website, along with the communication and informative materials.

In order to increase the visibility and traffic of the website, as well as the number of downloads of the reports and the deliverables an excessive campaign will be implemented via the other dissemination and communication channels such as LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook or blogs. Last but not least, several blog articles and other relevant projects that contained relevant keywords will be posted on the website to boost engine optimization.

Figure 1: MES-CoBraD Website

¹ <https://www.mes-cobrad.eu>

2 SOCIAL MEDIA

Digital and social media have tremendous potential for reaching some of the targeted audiences and engaging people with the MES-CoBraD project. Social Media provide an online platform for everyone who wants to interact and exchange opinions, knowledge and expertise. Social media platforms are very effective tools for projects to implement marketing and to achieve showcase of the project’s goals and strategies in the top search lists of search engine results for relevant queries. Through the use of the social media, MES-CoBraD can manage a steady flow of information towards audiences during the project’s lifetime and can sustain a well-informed audience which will enhance the project’s overall impact and outcome.

Appropriate pages designed depending on the channel and a content maintenance plan put in place for management the streaming of information across these channels to secure and maintain followers. Social and digital media will be particularly powerful in helping to create ‘communities of support’ for the project. The project will create interest on social media and digital platforms by using visual media, videos, animations, icons and info-graphic imagery, and importantly, mobile enabled content and richer content experiences for users.

The MES-CoBraD Dissemination and Communication Plan has chosen to create social media accounts on LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook and YouTube channel. Using content that matches the structural affordances of each platform and features SEO characteristics (e.g., relevant hashtags) combined with the partners’ already existing accounts, MES-CoBraD accounts are going to be used to increase project’s visibility in social networking sites.

MES-CoBraD social media platforms will be used in order to promote the action and its results more widely to every possible audience and therefore stakeholder. Hence, such communication platforms can promote the project and its activities by adapting its communication messages for searching relevant audiences.

The following table presents the aim and scope per social media channel.

Table 1: MES-CoBraD social media accounts

Social Media Channel	Purpose	Plan
LinkedIn	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the scientific and policymaking community	Ad hoc posts on project’s progress.
Twitter	Increase MES-CoBraD visibility in the scientific community, the policymaking community, and civil society.	1-2 posts per week on current affairs and project’s progress.
Facebook	Increase MES-CoBraD Visibility in the society.	1-2 posts per week on current affairs
YouTube	Useful for key messages	When a video is available

2.1 LINKEDIN

LinkedIn² is a business and employment-oriented social network allowing individuals and organisations to promote their professional progress and outcomes. MES-CoBraD page³ in LinkedIn will be used to target more specialised audiences within the framework of dissemination and exploitation. The MES-CoBraD account in LinkedIn is already online and available to all the scientific, policymaking and stakeholder community. The account has already 70 followers and 4 posts about all the important developments that happened until now in the duration of the project.

2.2 TWITTER

Twitter⁴ is an online social networking service on which users post and interact with short messages (less than 280 characters). It is ideal for short announcements of the action's outcomes and will be used ad hoc. Via its account⁵ in Twitter MES-CoBraD is envisaged to reach a wide variety of audiences suitable primarily for communication and dissemination purposes. More specifically, the MES-CoBraD account in Twitter is on and functional, also it has already 45 followers, and a lot of tweets and retweets about the CoBraD diseases.

2.3 FACEBOOK

Facebook⁶ is a social networking app for sharing photos and videos with other user and it is ideal for communicating with members of the general public. Via its channel⁷ MES-CoBraD will post pictures on health issues, such as CoBraD diseases, and will communicate its scope and objective to the wider public. The MES-CoBraD Facebook account is active and has already 27 people who like the page and 34 individuals who follow the account.

2.4 YOUTUBE

YouTube⁸ is a free video sharing website that makes it easy to everybody to watch online videos. YouTube gives the opportunity to the users to even create and upload their own videos to share with other users. Via YouTube channel MES-CoBraD will create and upload videos that are aligned with health issues about the CoBraD diseases. The first video⁹ is already uploaded in the YouTube channel of the MES-CoBraD project, the audience can reach it out through the website.

2.5 FUTURE STEPS

MES-CoBraD will use the above mentioned social media accounts to promote the actions and its results more widely to every possible stakeholder. These platforms have been identified as the most suitable to use. The MES-CoBraD coordinator will manage the social media accounts, whilst all partners will follow the accounts and publish information about events, activities, outputs, and results of the project.

Social Media Account Takeover by our partners may be promoted on special occasions,

² <https://linkedin.com>

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/mes-cobrad>

⁴ <https://twitter.com/>

⁵ <https://twitter.com/MESCoBraD>

⁶ <https://www.facebook.com>

⁷ <https://www.facebook.com/mescobrad/>

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com>

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pOgT-zDqC-U>

3 NEWS MEDIA CONTENT

In order to effectively disseminate and communicate MES-CoBraD towards the diverse set of stakeholders, the project's strategy must leverage the promotion possibilities of mass media channels, as well as to formulate its own media materials that will cover MES-CoBraD's development steps, networking actions and notable outcomes throughout its lifecycle. Therefore, MES-CoBraD's dissemination and communication planning must include specific methods that will be conducted as following:

3.1 NEWSLETTERS

Newsletters and e-Newsletters will be issued providing information on the project development and events. These newsletters will take as input information from all partners on progress and key outcomes of the project. The main goal of the newsletters is to increase the awareness about the ongoing work of the project and its relevance to the policymaking and stakeholder groups. Newsletters will be developed in English and will be translated in all project languages. Moreover, the newsletters will be published on the project's website, so there are readily accessible by all target groups across Europe. More specifically, the newsletters will be distributed by email to public authorities and other relevant stakeholders in each participating country.

It is envisaged that up to four newsletters will be developed and disseminated during the project duration which will regularly disseminate the project's achievements. The effectiveness of the newsletters' impact will be evaluated by a respective tool and reports, including openings, clicks and list of recipients.

The MES-CoBraD coordinator will manage the newsletters, whilst each partner will further promote the project's newsletters. The partners that publish company/organisation newsletters will further promote the project by including articles related to MES-CoBraD. More specifically, for the distribution of newsletters, each partner will ensure compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

3.2 BLOGS

The project will elaborate blogging as a dissemination and communication method that will provide updates in a sustainable frequency about the actions of Consortium members. Blogs will be used in order to communicate the interesting achievements that result from the application of the social analysis as academic publications in high-calibre media websites. These websites often feature opinion articles from external sources in their "Opinion" columns, so it is possible to include articles regarding MES-CoBraD as well.

It is envisaged that the MES-CoBraD project will have ten blog entries the first year, which will regularly communicate the results of the project in the academic community.

3.3 PRESS RELEASES

A press release is a formal announcement of the project to the national, European and international press. Press releases are issued to announce important news and achievements, as well as workshops and events that are organised by project partners. Moreover, occasionally press releases may be circulated to various stakeholders and interested parties in case there is a specific need.

Press releases will be distributed in the course of Specialized newspapers and magazines of wide acceptance and circulation will be selected for the publications. Finally, it is envisaged that at least six press releases will be circulated in non-academic sources.

4 PUBLICATIONS

All the partners of the project produce reports on technical aspects of MES-CoBraD. This material is valuable in terms of disseminate the project's goal, developments and results. Thus, all this material is going to be disclosed in platforms where it will be able to reach adequate audiences, such as researchers and pundits of the relative scientific domains. In particular, in the following sections are described the two major data repositories that the deliverable reports are planned to be uploaded. The main role of these data repositories is to accumulate and secure the accessibility for knowledge that derives from the MES-CoBraD project.

4.1.1 OPENAIRE

OpenAire¹⁰ is a science-related portal, the mission of which is to provide unlimited, barrier-free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. The use of OpenAIRE will enable MES-CoBraD, on one hand, to report more effectively the scientific outcomes of the action and, on the other hand, to reach a wide community of scientists and stakeholders interested in EU-funded research in general.

4.1.2 ZENODO

Zenodo¹¹ is a data repository developed by CERN within the framework of OpenAIRE, welcoming all science data around the globe. Its main purpose is to provide an easy-access data repository for scientific data from all over the world and from every discipline. MES-CoBraD uses Zenodo, in order to provide open access to its outcomes, and disseminate them to appropriate audiences at the same time.

All the published materials of MES-CoBraD project are available through the website and the corresponding repository communities, Zenodo¹² and OpenAIRE¹³.

Table 2: MES-CoBraD Published Material up to October 2021

Delivery No.	Name	Type	Date
1	Project Manual – CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation	Report	August 2021
2	Communication & Dissemination plan	Report	August 2021
3	MES-CoBraD Website	Websites, patents filling, etc.	August 2021
4	Promotional and Informational Material	Websites, patents filling, etc.	October 2021
5	Report on the Registration of the Studies	Report	October 2021
6	Establishment of External Advisory Board	Report	October 2021

¹⁰ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹² <https://zenodo.org/communities/mes-cobrad/>

¹³ <https://explore.openaire.eu/MES-CoBraD>

5 PARTNER'S EVENTS

5.1 WORKSHOPS

Workshops are small interactive events held to achieve a specific objective. A workshop could be used to get feedback from users on the proposed solution or to get feedback from experts on a particular issue. MES-CoBraD workshops will be implemented in order to actively attain the objectives of current strategy and raise awareness. Moreover, the workshops will be organized at regional and national level in which the stakeholders will be informed on the goal, developments, results and models of the solution that offers the MES-CoBraD project. In the workshops, the specifications of the MES-CoBraD platform as well as questions will be co-formulated with the stakeholders. Furthermore, in the workshops, stakeholders will be informed on global, regional and national pathways including actions about the CoBraD diseases and solutions that will positively impact the patients.

Finally, the MES-CoBraD consortium is planning to organize minimum three workshops in order to communicate the goals, achievements, developments and results to policymakers, stakeholders, patients and other groups of audience.

5.2 PRESENTATIONS

Scientific presentation is an important part of the communication and dissemination strategy of disseminate the project's results to the research community. Moreover, partners of the MES-CoBraD project are highly encouraged to participate in events and deliver presentations on the project's scope, goal, objectives, developments and expected results. More specifically, the most important thing of the presentations is the opportunity to share the project's achievements with experts in the field and also raise interest among other target groups.

Moreover, a detailed project presentation template has been created, allowing the partners to embed basic information into the presentations. The presentation will be used by the MES-CoBraD consortium to present the objectives, target groups, methodological framework, expected results and serve as the main presentation tool, for dissemination purposes at relevant events.

5.3 OTHER RELEVANT EVENTS

According to the Grant Agreement, the consortium has already planned training activities and other events targeting participants from the MES-CoBraD project. More specifically, the approach of such events is directed to initially create general awareness of the project objectives, goal and results. Moreover, during the project, online and offline meetings will be prepared and implements for knowledge exchange with the policymakers and the stakeholder groups.

Lastly, a final project event will be organised at the end of the project in order to disseminate its results. Researchers, doctors, security and IoT organisations will be the main target groups of this final conference.

6 INFOGRAPHICS & VIDEOS

Due to the information overload, which is a typical characteristic of the latest years, it is very important to use visual means of promotion such as infographics and videos.

6.1 INFOGRAPHICS

The production of infographics is necessary to the MES-CoBraD project in order to show the results in a clear and simple way. More specifically, appropriately designed infographics will be produced during the project implementation phase, in order to convey to policymakers and other stakeholders the MES-CoBraD results through comprehensive visual representations. Furthermore, infographics make broad of ideas more simplified since they combine images, colours and other visual means. Finally, infographics can be used to illustrate how the development of innovations and strategies can have impacts on the costs and benefits of different societal and technological transitions.

6.2 VIDEOS

Videos will be used in order to disseminate the MES-CoBraD results in a more effective way to all the audiences of the project. The production of the videos will be presenting the project's activities in English, with subtitled versions for all project languages. It is foreseen that a total of five videos targeted at policymakers and other stakeholders' groups will be produced and circulated during the project's lifetime. Last but not least, one video is already published through the website of the project in the YouTube channel of MES-CoBraD.

7 C&D PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS AVAILABLE ONLINE

7.1 FLYER

In the project flyer basic information about its action is included aiming at creating visibility about the project and all partners involved. The size of the flyer is A5 nominal and includes a brief description of the project, the MES-CoBraD consortium member institutes' logos and the project Contact Information.

The MES-CoBraD Project Flyer will be distributed at conferences, meetings, workshops and other events within the scientific and stakeholder communities. The first version produced is in English and is available both electronically and in hard copy. In the near future it will be translated in all partners' languages.

The digital version of the Flyer will be available for download in the MES-CoBraD Website.

For MES-CoBraD to successfully realise its vision, a set of objectives are set, covering the project's scientific, technological and societal aspects throughout its duration as well as the exploitation of the project's results after its end. The overall project success will be defined by the efficiency and effectiveness of the appropriate synthesis, as well as the individual quality of the specific achievements related to the project's objectives, clearly measured by specific key performance indicators. MES-CoBraD will pursue its realization through objectives that fall under three main categories.

Scientific objectives focusing on the scientific and research work to be done to deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles. Technical objectives focusing on the delivery of the MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and Societal objectives that focus on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2021 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 965422.

Figure 2: MES-CobraD Flyer, front page

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) objective is to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD). MES-CoBraD will co-develop along with experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing & communication across Europe, a novel and demand-driven framework focused on improving the quality of life for patients, their caregivers, and the society at large. The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

Visit us in our web: www.mes-cobrad.eu

Contact Details

 MES-CoBraD
 @MESCoBraD
 MES-CoBraD

Figure 3: MES-CoBraD flyer, back page

7.2 LEAFLET

A MES-CoBraD Leaflet has been designed and produced for the aim of the dissemination and communication strategy among academic researchers, Research producing Organisations, Industry, Policy Makers, Citizen Scientists, Research Infrastructures and e-infrastructures, Health providers (private and public), Patients, patient advocates and the general public, at conferences meetings, workshops, or other events within the scientific, industry and to all other interested parties. The promotional leaflet briefly describes the aims, objectives, contents, expected results and consortium synthesis of the project. The leaflet is a trifold and consists of six distinctive panels/sections.

The first version of the leaflet is produced in English in A4 size and will be available both electronically and in hard copy. It will be translated in all partners' languages while the digital version of the MES-CoBraD Leaflet will be available for download in the MES-CoBraD Website.

Figure 4: MES-CoBraD Leaflet – Outer side

Figure 5: MES-CoBraD Leaflet – Inner side

7.3 POSTER

A publicity poster for MES-CoBraD has been created and will be used as promotional material at events organised by the partners or hosted by other relevant organisations or the European Commission. The Poster will be further updated in the future to reflect the project achievements and results in an effort to convey new information in line with the project progress. The digital version of the MES-CoBraD Poster will be available for download in the MES-CoBraD Website.

The Poster will be produced in two sizes, A3 and A0, to be used according to the needs of the event, at which it will be presented.

The poster includes:

1. The MES-CoBraD concept
2. The project's objectives, novelties and approach
3. Partners' Logos
4. Contact Information
5. Textual and graphic elements

The MES-CoBraD Project Poster is presented in the following figure.

Figure 6: MES-CoBraD Poster

7.4 ROLLUP

A MES-CoBraD Roll-up has been created for future events organised by the project partners or hosted by other relevant organisations. The logo and the project goals and targets are displayed in the top center. All images, graphic and textual elements are selected in order to be clear and easy to read. The colours blue, light blue and white are in coherence with the project's visual identity. Social media channels are placed in the bottom parts. The Roll-up size is about 80 cm X 200 cm. It is portable and has its own retracting mechanism built from aluminium, which enables easy portability and setup.

In the Roll-up the following are included:

- › The logo and title of the project
- › Textual and graphic elements on the I2AM PARIS Platform, Climate Policies, and Co-Creation
- › Partners' Logos
- › Social media channels

The digital version of the MES-CoBraD Roll-up will be available for download in the MES-CoBraD Website.
The MES-CoBraD Roll - up is shown in the following figure.

Figure 7: MES-CoBraD Roll-up

7.5 ARTICLES

Appropriate articles aiming to the targeted audience will be disseminated via the aforementioned promotional channels (websites, blogs, etc.). Depending on the desired outcome, these articles may focus on MES-CoBraD and its societal impacts in general or be more specific by promoting individual project outcomes.

A standard article containing basic information about MES-CoBraD will be produced in order to be online for dissemination purposes at relevant events. It is envisaged that the MES-CoBraD project will publish a lot of articles throughout the lifetime of the project in order to communicate the goal, developments and results with its audience.

8 FUTURE STEPS

All the above materials will be constantly updated and uploaded to the project website, during the lifecycle of the project from all partners, always according to the needs not only of the project, but also of the stakeholders and other audiences. More specifically, in the Deliverable 9.6 “Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities Report and Plan” future communication & dissemination material and tools will be added, and all progress of the dissemination and communication activities will be recorded and presented.

